

THE IMPORTANCE OF ONLINE JOURNALISM TODAY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7030868>

Annotation: this article is written about points that prove that online journalism is related to the media of the current era.

Keywords: online, global, newspaper, internet, media:

Although the media began to use the internet at the beginning of the 21st century, until that time there were various disputes over whether it was a full-fledged media. During the years of the global network's entry into the life of the media, the conflict of concepts on this topic will last longer. The fate of various positions that recognize the internet as a media tool makes it possible to more rationally understand the changes that the media are facing today and modern journalism in general affects the content of the topic. Among some of its researchers, it is worth noting that the conflicts on this issue are ongoing, since their surroundings are characterized by an unconscious tension. Russian scientist Akopov says that there will be no exaggeration if the internet is interpreted as a global media. He argues that the approach to computer electronic networks as a new media is also a question of typologizing this type of mass media. In contrast to him, Davidov denies the concept of the internet media, describing the internet as the next Information carrier, and media has a common field in which carriers can be divided into types. It also considers the environment as well as the body, which allows to eliminate conflicts between the types of information carriers and summarize their advantages in a single media. Some experts, on the other hand, support another opinion. According to a number of observations, so far the internet cannot enter into competition with traditional media. This review, which everyone has surpassed them according to some criteria due to its technical capabilities, has several grounds. Firstly, not all the inhabitants of the planet are equally used by the online media, and secondly, the word internet interest is about such a type of journalistic activity that is theoretically not fully formed as journalism. A group of scientists say that the role of newspapers or other traditional media is determined by internet connections, while predicting the future of traditional media in the era of the internet at an early stage. Local researchers recognize that the possibilities of Information Technology provide quality research in the traditional press of Uzbekistan. Obviously, the use of technologies in the usual mass media system

provides additional opportunities for the transmission and distribution of information, creating methods of new forms of mass informational influence. Some believe that a new means of information delivery will allow the traditional media to be reborn. This opinion is justified by the fact that the media, considered typical for the media, view the internet only as a source of information, and as a result, their level relies significantly on enrichment. Other scientists believe that technological capabilities will turn the network into a fully promising, but to a lesser extent, an alternative non-traditional media. And in a number of European countries and the United States, a decrease in the audience of readers is felt by traditional press publications therein. Analysts, on the other hand, emphasize that in response to this situation, the media is obliged to radically change in order to survive in such conditions. According to scientists from the Association of publishing and technology should have all the appearance not only in print, that is, in order to maintain its position in the media, the transfer of information through two or several means of passing through the voice from the distribution of information through one channel. From theorists, in thought, in editorial offices, practicing experts believe that each type of media has its own task, and it is this trait that ensures their uniqueness.

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